

Data Uji Coba Aplikasi Prediksi Kegemukan Pada Remaja Berdasarkan Faktor Risiko untuk 100 Responden

No	Nama	Nama Sekolah	BB (Kg)	TB (Cm)	IMT	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19	P20	Pengetahuan	Lama aktivitas	Jumlah Sayur	Konsumsi Lemak	Konsumsi Karbo	Total	P(X)	Prediksi (%)
1	1	SMA N 7 PADANG	67,0	168	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0,0076	0,8
2	2	SMA N 7 PADANG	45,0	156	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	0,0034	0,3
3	3	SMA N 7 PADANG	37,0	154	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	0,3970	39,7	
4	4	SMA N 7 PADANG	41,0	153	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2
5	5	SMA N 7 PADANG	66,0	153	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	4	0,6592	65,9
6	6	SMA N 7 PADANG	41,0	140	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	2	0,0192	1,9
7	7	SMA N 7 PADANG	42,0	153	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2
8	8	SMA N 7 PADANG	80,0	153	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3
9	9	SMA N 7 PADANG	78,0	148	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3
10	10	SMA N 7 PADANG	46,0	146	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2
11	11	SMA N 7 PADANG	47,0	173	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	3	0,1072	10,7	
12	12	SMA N 7 PADANG	45,0	154	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	2	0,0085	0,9	
13	13	SMA N 7 PADANG	70,0	158	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	4	0,6130	61,3	
14	14	SMA N 7 PADANG	42,0	158	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0,0029	0,3	
15	15	SMA N 7 PADANG	79,0	175	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	3	0,0202	2,0
16	16	SMA N 7 PADANG	44,0	162	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	2	0,0085	0,9	
17	17	SMA N 7 PADANG	68,0	140	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	4	0,2495	24,9	
18	18	SMA N 7 PADANG	70,0	156	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
19	19	SMA N 7 PADANG	46,0	156	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	4	0,2495	24,9	
20	20	SMA N 7 PADANG	52,0	171	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	2	0,0220	2,2		
21	21	SMA N 7 PADANG	88,0	159	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	4	0,6130	61,3	
22	22	SMA N 8 PADANG	45,0	163	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	3	0,0202	2,0		
23	23	SMA N 8 PADANG	48,0	166	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2	
24	24	SMA N 8 PADANG	80,0	162	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
25	25	SMA N 8 PADANG	40,0	146	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	3	0,1072	10,7	
26	26	SMA N 8 PADANG	62,0	157	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
27	27	SMA N 8 PADANG	55,0	153	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	3	0,1214	12,1	
28	28	SMA N 8 PADANG	65,0	163	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	3	0,0895	9,0	
29	29	SMA N 8 PADANG	54,0	153	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	3	0,2397	24,0		
30	30	SMA N 8 PADANG	68,0	157	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
31	31	SMA N 10 PADAN	48,0	156	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	4	0,6592	65,9	
32	32	SMA N 10 PADAN	39,0	150	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	2	0,0220	2,2	
33	33	SMA N 10 PADAN	41,0	156	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	2	0,0181	1,8	
34	34	SMA N 10 PADAN	45,0	152	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	4	0,4314	43,1	
35	35	SMA N 10 PADAN	64,0	153	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	4	0,6592	65,9	
36	36	SMA N 10 PADAN	52,0	155	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	2	0,0449	4,5	
37	37	SMA N 10 PADAN	38,0	158	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	2	0,0085	0,9	
38	38	SMA N 10 PADAN	90,0	163	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
39	39	SMA N 10 PADAN	59,0	146	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	3	0,3970	39,7		
40	40	SMA N 10 PADAN	47,0	169	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	3	0,1214	12,1		
41	41	SMA N 10 PADAN	63,0	157	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	4	0,6130	61,3	
42	42	SMA N 10 PADAN	60,0	161	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2	
43	43	SMA N 10 PADAN	37,0	150	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2
44	44	SMA N 10 PADAN	67,0	171	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0,0011	0,1		
45	45	SMA N 10 PADAN	44,0	166	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	2	0,0449	4,5			
46	46	SMA N 10 PADAN	68,0	154	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	4	0,6130	61,3		
47	47	SMA N 10 PADAN	39,0	157	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0,0011	0,1	
48	48	SMA N 10 PADAN	50,0	160	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	3	0,1016	10,2		
49	49	SMA N 10 PADAN	65,0	160	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3		
50	50	SMA N 10 PADAN	60,0	153	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	4	0,6130	61,3		
51	51	SMA N 10 PADAN	45,0	170	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0,0029	0,3			

No	Nama	Nama Sekolah	BB (Kg)	TB (Cm)	IMT	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19	P20	Pengetahuan	Lama aktivitas	Jumlah Sayur	Konsumsi Lemak	Konsumsi Karbo	Total	P(X)	Prediksi (%)	
52	52	SMA N 10 PADAN	37,0	148	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	3	0,0895	9,0	
53	53	SMA N 10 PADAN	49,0	168	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	2	0,0393	3,9	
54	54	SMA N 10 PADAN	71,0	163	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	3	0,3970	39,7		
55	55	SMA N 10 PADAN	45,0	160	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2	
56	56	SMA N 10 PADAN	43,0	164	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	3	0,0202	2,0	
57	57	SMA Adabiah Padang	74,0	157	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	4	0,6130	61,3	
58	58	SMA Adabiah Padang	56,0	163	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	2	0,0449	4,5
59	59	SMA Adabiah Padang	56,0	174	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	0,0449	4,5
60	60	SMA Adabiah Padang	40,0	153	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	3	0,0514	5,1	
61	61	SMA Adabiah Padang	44,0	162	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2
62	62	SMA Adabiah Padang	60,0	156	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
63	63	SMA Adabiah Padang	42,0	143	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	4	0,2495	24,9
64	64	SMA Adabiah Padang	54,0	154	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	3	0,1214	12,1
65	65	SMA Adabiah Padang	79,0	152	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	4	0,6592	65,9	
66	66	SMA Adabiah Padang	69,0	173	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	2	0,0449	4,5
67	67	SMA Adabiah Padang	88,0	160	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	2	0,0449	4,5
68	68	SMA Adabiah Padang	62,0	156	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
69	69	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	56,0	174	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0,0076	0,8
70	70	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	50,0	167	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	3	0,0514	5,1	
71	71	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	58,0	164	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	2	0,0220	2,2	
72	72	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	45,0	154	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0,0076	0,8
73	73	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	65,0	156	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
74	74	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	36,0	164	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,0005	0,0	
75	75	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	39,0	150	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2	
76	76	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	45,0	153	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0,0029	0,3	
77	77	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	54,0	170	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0,0076	0,8
78	78	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	80,0	164	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
79	79	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	74,0	168	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	2	0,0181	1,8
80	80	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	51,0	164	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	3	0,1214	12,1	
81	81	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	59,0	153	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	4	0,6130	61,3	
82	82	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	46,0	155	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	2	0,0449	4,5
83	83	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	45,0	146	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	4	0,2495	24,9	
84	84	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	66,0	163	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
85	85	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	63,0	160	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	3	0,1214	12,1
86	86	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	40,0	162	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	4	0,2495	24,9	
87	87	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	66,0	160	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	3	0,1214	12,1	
88	88	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	55,0	171	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0,0005	0,0	
89	89	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	60,0	154	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
90	90	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	55,0	168	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	4	0,2495	24,9	
91	91	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	42,0	148	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	2	0,0220	2,2	
92	92	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	50,0	160	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0,0029	0,3	
93	93	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	61,0	156	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3	
94	94	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	35,0	149	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0,0076	0,8	
95	95	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	45,0	154	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0,0029	0,3	
96	96	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	53,0	164	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	2	0,0449	4,5
97	97	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	61,0	158	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2
98	98	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	85,0	161	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	0,8231	82,3		
99	99	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	49,0	150	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	3	0,1016	10,2	
100	100	SMA Kartika 1-Padang	34,0	154	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0,0014	0,1	

Keterangan :

No	Nama	Nama Sekolah	BB (Kg)	TB (Cm)	IMT	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19	P20	Pengetahuan	Lama aktivitas	Jumlah Sayur	Konsumsi Lemak	Konsumsi Karbo	Total	P(X)	Prediksi (%)
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Putih = Status gizi normal, status gizi normal

Hijau = Status gizi normal, gemuk

Kuning = Gemuk, gemuk

Merah = Gemuk, status gizi normal